

Research Symposium: AI in MENA: Authoritarian Governance, Global Competition, and Sociopolitical Impact

Introduction by Eric Lob and Selin Bengi Gümürkçü

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Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly emerging as an important force shaping many aspects of political, economic, and social life. Yet its implications, particularly political ones, are far from uniform and are mediated by regional contexts and institutional configurations. In the Middle East and North Africa (MENA), AI has already emerged to be much more than a mere technological innovation. It is also a politically embedded instrument through which economic futures are imagined, state power and popular dissent are exercised, and global positioning is renegotiated. This symposium examines how Arab Gulf states and others in the region are integrating AI into authoritarian governance, competing in the international AI race, and

cooperating with the United States and China in the process. It also explores the technology's sociopolitical, cultural, religious, and ethical implications.

The significance of AI for MENA stems in part from the region's ongoing efforts to navigate enduring structural challenges. They include, but are not limited to, economic diversification, demographic change, domestic discontent, and military conflict. In this context, AI is perceived and portrayed as a solution to some of these challenges. Using AI to diversify their economies, Arab Gulf states have aggressively positioned themselves as AI hubs within the global economy. As Yasir Atalan shows, these states have done so by

investing in data centers, cloud infrastructure, and corporate partnerships. In the process, they expect that AI will enable them to transform key industries, enhance productivity, and generate new sources of revenue and employment. From the perspective of path dependency, Andrew Leber posits that the efforts and expectations of these states concerning the critical juncture of the AI revolution are conditioned and constrained by pre-existing parameters, such as past investments in state-owned enterprises, power grids, and human resources.

In addition to being economically important, AI is increasingly central to governance practices across the region, from public service delivery and urban management to state surveillance and information control. As Alexandra Siegel argues, the expansion of data infrastructures and algorithmic tools has enhanced state capacity while also raising concerns about the deepening of authoritarian practices, particularly in countries where institutional constraints remain limited. It also creates ethical and legal problems regarding surveillance technologies, as Abdullah Omran suggests. At the same time, the political significance of AI in MENA extends beyond state strategies. Non-state actors and various opposition forces are also engaging with AI and incorporating it into practices of communication and mobilization.

As with other areas, AI in MENA is shaped by global hierarchies and dependencies. As Guy Burton asserts, the region's efforts to become an AI hub are embedded in transnational technological ecosystems dominated by major powers and multinational corporations. Questions surrounding data sovereignty, infrastructural development, and regulatory alignment reflect broader geopolitical dynamics, as states navigate between integra-

tion into global systems and aspirations for digital autonomy.

Inside MENA, AI should also be considered in relation to the persistent phenomenon of orientalism. As Adib-Moghadam argues, contemporary AI systems are largely developed from a Euro-American technological and epistemological frame of reference. Consequently, they are embedded with Euro-centric assumptions, classifications, and biases that reproduce reductionist and essentialist representations of MENA societies. These dynamics risk reinforcing longstanding orientalist tropes and depicting the region as exceptional, unstable, and culturally static. This is particularly the case with applications, such as automated content moderation, security profiling, and data classification, where contextual nuance is often limited.

Taken together, these developments underscore that AI matters for MENA. It is not only a set of technological tools, but a domain through which longstanding political and socioeconomic questions are being raised and reconfigured. By situating AI within the region's specific institutional and geopolitical contexts, this symposium stresses the need for rigorous, grounded analysis of the interplay among technology, power, and transformation. ♦